

Factors Affecting The Students' Perception On Quality Education

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***Abstract:** Ensuring quality in education is a continuous process. But knowing the pivotal factors of quality education can provide a guideline to the education providers to meet this standard. With this aim, this research is undertaken to unveil the factors that contribute to education quality. To do so, 245 undergraduate business students are selected from four renowned public and private universities in Bangladesh to collect their opinion. Study reveals that Qualified Faculties play major role to ensure the quality education. Organization & Management's effort, Development of Personal skills, Learning Resources, Academic Support are also the important factors for the quality education. Teaching Quality is the most significant factor to ensure the quality education followed by Personal Development, Organizational and Management Approach, Learning Resources, Academic Support. It is also discovered that, students do not consider Assessment and Feedback mechanism is a parameter to judge the education standard of a university.*

1.0 Introduction

Quality education defines as ensuring the standard of all aspect of education. In the higher education, it is affected by many issues like- teaching methods, logistic support, self-development of the students. Based on the higher education philosophy, vision and mission, it is clear that the faculties are consistently positive towards ensuring the quality education and appeared to be very dynamic in the quality approach and its technique. According to Berry & Parasuraman (1992), the strategic success of a service organization depends on the ability of service providers to enhance their images by consistently meeting or exceeding customers' service expectation. These components must be measured regularly to respond to the changes of the environments where the expectation of the stakeholder is becoming higher. The outcomes of the measurement are very useful for the faculties, administrators as well as the academic staffs to provide plans and solutions for the continuous improvement.

It is vital to consistently measure the performance of service quality from student perspective because they are directly involved in the education process. They act as a consumer or customer and also as a product of the education institution. Students' views on all aspects of their higher education experiences are essential to monitor the quality of education. The data and information gained will help the service provider and the stakeholder to make judgments about level of quality in particular universities (Hill, Lomas, & MacGregor, 2003). The development of the dimensions in service quality is expanding because the nature of the higher learning institution itself is dynamic and

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unique. One of the methods to construct the dimension of quality in education is the dimensions of product, software and general services. Apart from that the modification for adaptation must be made to tailor it to the education line. Furthermore, the construct or the dimension of quality conceptualized in the service literature focus on perceived quality. Conceptually, perceived quality is defined as the consumer's judgment about an overall entity of excellence or superiority (Zeithaml, 1987). It is a form of overall evaluation. Gordon & Partigon (1993) characterize that education quality is the success with which an institution provides educational environments which enable students effectively to achieve worthwhile learning goals including appropriate academic standards.

Meeting the education standards is not an easy to go matter rather it requires closer look into this issue. Defining and ensuring quality education is always critical and subjective in nature. Thus continuous research and evaluation are necessary to improve the education quality. This research aims to discover the important issues involve in quality education which could be the useful guideline for the education providers in many country like Bangladesh.

1.1 Objective of the study

This study is conducted to find out the significant factors affecting the education quality from the student perspective. Therefore, we will be able to generalize these factors on the education institutions and also to recommend which area(s) that needs to improve.

1.2 Significance of the study

Our study will contribute to further exploratory or descriptive research in this area. Though our research is solely based on the student's perspective, academic experts will be able to find out the students demand about the quality education. Experts can make a breeze between the students demand and their offerings. The outcome of this study is also useful for the management and the faculty to continuously improve the service quality of education.

2.0 Literature Review

This chapter discusses the literature on the quality management background, definition of quality, the dimensions and the approach in measuring quality and the factors that influence the evaluation of service quality in education. It is vital to review all the relevant literatures in order to understand the whole concept of quality education, its tools and application in various sectors. It explores a strong basis for the development of the research framework and instrument.

2.1 Definition of quality

The study of students' perception regarding quality education has drawn much attention in the previous researches. Quality is a perceptual, conditional and somewhat subjective attribute and may be understood differently by different people (Motala, 2000). Quality can be defined in many ways. It can be seen and can be measured. A number of researchers have worked on this "quality" term and have given various definitions on

quality in particular areas, i.e, manufacturing of products and services. Garvin (1984) has classified the definition of quality into five major groups. Those are transcendent, product-based, user-based, manufacturing-based, or value-based. Others define quality as fitness for use (Juran & Gryna, 1988), conformance to requirement (Crosby, 1979), conformance to specification (Gilmore. 1974), meeting and/or exceeding customers' expectation (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1985), performance over expectation (Besterfield, 1999), zero defect (Crosby, 1979), products' or services' ability to perform to its intended function without harmful effect (Taguchi, 1986).

Although there is no universally accepted definition of quality and seems to be no consensus definition even though most of these definitions are correlated, but there have similarity and common elements on its definition. According to Geotsch & Davis (2003), with these common elements extracted, quality can be defined as a dynamic state associated with products, services, people, processes, and environments that meets or exceeds customer expectation.

In the area of education, Cheng (1995) defines education quality is the character of the set of elements in the input, process, and output of the education system that provides services that completely satisfy both internal and external strategic constituencies by meeting their explicit and implicit expectations. In addition, Harvey & Green (1993) propose five ways of thinking about quality in education. *First*, quality is regarded in term of excellence. *Second*, quality is perfection or consistency. *Third*, quality is fitness for purpose. *Forth*, quality is value for money and *finally*, quality is transformation processes that have value-added activities.

This definition also takes into account the global and international influences that drive the discussion of educational quality (Motala, 2000), while ensuring that national and local educational contexts contribute to definitions of quality in varying countries (Adams, 1993). Establishing a contextualized understanding of quality includes relevant stakeholders. Key stakeholders often hold different views and meanings of educational quality (Motala, 2000; Benoliel, O'Gara, & Miske, 1999).

2.2 The Meaning of Education Quality

The precise meaning of education quality and the path to improvement of quality are often left unexplained. It can be defined as the inputs (numbers of teachers, amount of teacher training, number of textbooks), processes (amount of direct instructional time, extent of active learning), outputs (test scores, graduation rates), and outcomes (performance in subsequent employment). Additionally, quality education may imply simply the attaining of specified targets and objectives. More comprehensive views are also found, and interpretation of quality may be based on an institution's or program's reputation, the extent to which learning has influenced change in student knowledge, attitudes, values, and behavior, or a complete theory or ideology of acquisition and application of learning (Adams, 1998).

In Lamanga's (2006) report on quality assurance in tertiary education in the case of Bangladesh, he recommends several initiatives that can ultimately ensure a quality education system for the higher learning institutions in the country. Aminuzzaman (2007)

opines that most of the departments of universities do not have a long-term national vision, but that such a vision is crucial to quality education.

According to Aminuzzaman (2007), quality education in universities will be achieved through changing the method of teaching and learning as well as assessment methods, renewing the curriculum continually, updating and upgrading professional knowledge and skills and improving the broader educational, administrative and resource environments. Actually, the student-lecturer interface is important in determining quality, and it is appropriate to seek to monitor this quality through appropriate quality assurance processes. Though this is a superficial approach, the real challenge is the enhancement of quality. Different institutions have started to investigate approaches to quality enhancement (Rowley & Nielsen, 1996). For instance, Hart & Shoolbred (1993) cite, Wolverhampton University is seeking registration under BS 5750 and a number of other universities are taking the TQM path, including Aston, South Bank, Robert Gordons and Wolverhampton. A paper by the further Education Unit (1991) offers six criteria for a quality model: (1) it seeks to improve the quality of teaching and learning strategies, (2) it is flexible, (3) it harnesses the commitment of all staff, (4) the learner should be involved, (5) there must be enhanced working relationships associated with all functions of the organization, and (6) requirements can be measured and progress can be demonstrated.

2.3 Teacher Feedback Mechanism

Assessment and feedback play a pivotal role in the process of education. In higher education assessments have increased importance as they are of interest not only to students and teachers but also to future employers and all stake holders in the process of education. Assessment practices have therefore been studied very closely. Ramsden (2000) remarks that the assessment of students is a serious and often tragic enterprise sums up the importance placed on assessments. Assessments have to be considered by both educators and students as a vital part of the process of education not as an appendage which is painstaking and laborious. Biggs (2000) points out the need to change the erroneous perception of assignments as a necessary evil, the bad news of teaching and learning, to be conducted at the end of all the good stuff. Assessments should not be viewed as a system that allows teachers to define, select, classify, motivate and report on students (Ramsden, 2000). This is explained as the backwash effect when the assessment determines student learning, rather than the official curriculum (Biggs, 2000).

Good teachers are skilled not only in instructional methods, but also in feedback and assessment practices which includes marking criteria, comments, marking intension that will allow them to gauge individual student learning and adapt activities according to student needs (Carron & Chau, 1996). This process should also include both performance assessment and assessment of factual knowledge. Many teachers and educational systems continue to rely almost exclusively on traditional paper-and-pencil tests of factual knowledge that tend to promote rote memorization rather than higher order thinking skills (Colby, 2000). The study of Dunn, Burbine, Bowers, & Tantleff-Dunn (2004) reveals that to avoid this problem teachers should focus more on feedback style which will ensure the effectiveness of the overall feedback system.

2.4 Teaching Style

While many people have argued that style is important in teaching, identifying the elements of our styles as teachers has proved to be difficult. One reason is that traditionally the concept of style has been viewed in a critical manner. It has been confused with affection, denigrated as a kind of posturing to mask a lack of substance or tolerated as a natural manifestation of personal eccentricities (Eble, 1980). Thus to define teaching style, it entails moving beyond the negative sense in which it is sometimes perceived.

Daniel (2004) thinks that teaching style refers to the teaching strategies and methods employed and use of certain kinds of rhetoric. But often, the literature only focuses on one of these dimensions. The term itself has no agreed definition but the more widely accepted definitions refer to it as a set of teaching tactics (Galton, Simon, & Croll, 1980).

Understanding the teaching style would be enhanced if we had a list of elements of style that we can use as a basis for examining the impact of teaching style on the students' perception regarding education quality. There is however, no clear consensus about the common components of style. Therefore, Teaching style should include general modes of classroom behavior, qualification of the teacher, teaching methods, personality traits, enthusiasm, metaphors of teaching.

2.5 Personal Development

Personal development has been at the heart of education in the West in the form of the Greek philosophers and in the East with Confucius (Craig, Richard, & Joy, 1998). Some people emphasize personal development as a part of quality education. It is found that there is one thing more than another which absolutely requires free activity on the part of the individual, it is precisely education, whose object it is to develop the individual.

During the 1960s a large increase in the number of students on American campuses led to research on the personal development needs of undergraduate students. Chickering & Reisser (1993) define seven vectors of personal development for young adults during their undergraduate years. These are - developing confidence, developing good communication skill, managing emotions, achieving autonomy and interdependence, developing mature interpersonal relationships, establishing identity, developing integrity.

In the UK, personal development takes a central place in university policy in 1997 when the Dearing Report declares that universities should go beyond academic teaching to provide students with personal development. Another research study of Rowley & Nielsen (1996) reveals that personal development of the students greatly depends on the development of students' communication skill, confidence, integrity and tackling unfamiliar problems.

2.6 Organization and Management Support

Students vary in their relationships with the university from transactional to highly relational bonds (Garbarino & Johnson, 1999). Regarding the relationships, two factors are important for higher student satisfaction. These are bonding and empathy between the organization and management. Bonding is defined as the dimension of a relationship that results in three parties (student, management and university) acting in a unified manner toward a desired goal (Oliver, Peter, Raymond, Jenny, Leo, & Alan, 2000). Family, professors, university personnel, reference groups, and social norms may be influential on bonding to organizations (Garbarino & Johnson, 1999). In the same manner, empathy is defined as trying to understand someone's desires and goals (Oliver et al., 2000). According to these researchers, there are indicated links of reciprocity and empathy to relationship marketing which will lead to efficient timetable, effective communication for the involved parties and the outcome of the positive blender of these elements will be well organized courses and learning resources (Arnett, German, & Hunt, 2003).

2.7 Learning Resources

Physical learning environments or the places, in which formal learning occurs, range from relatively modern and well-equipped buildings to open-air gathering places. The quality of school facilities seems to have an indirect effect on learning, an effect that is hard to measure. Fuller & Dellagnelo (1999) argue that present empirical evidence is inconclusive as to whether the condition of school buildings is related to higher student achievement after taking into account student's background. A study in India has found that out of 59 schools, forty nine schools have good library facilities, and of these 59, twenty five have excellent IT facilities, twenty have multimedia facilities, and maximum of them have specialized class room facilities (Carron & Chau, 1996). In this case, the quality of the education environment was strongly correlated with pupils' achievement in Hindi and mathematics (Carron & Chau, 1996). In Latin America, a study has included 5,000 graduate students and found that students whose universities lacke classroom materials and has an inadequate library are significantly more likely to show lower test scores and higher grade repetition than those whose universities are well equipped (Willms, 2000).

Higher education is by its nature a developmental environment (Rowley & Nielsen, 1996). Classroom facilities are important because they are part of the whole atmosphere of learning, which includes elements such as modern teaching aids with rich libraries as well as neat and clean space that is adequate in terms of class size, it resources and temperature environment. In Bangladesh, most of the private universities are established via rental and classroom space is alarmingly inadequate. This factor is, thus, important in evaluating the perception level of the students regarding quality education. But in case of public universities we can see the opposite scenario (Ashraf, Ibrahim, & Joarder, 2009).

2.8 Academic Support

MaGuire, Jacobowitz, Weinstein, & Luekens (2006) argue that student affairs staffs are responsible for academic advising and support services delivery at colleges and

universities all over the world. The chief student affairs officer at a college or university often reports directly to the chief executive of the institution. In addition to that, student affairs professionals are charged with the daily tasks of developing programs and researching techniques that benefit all students as a whole (Dungy, Komives, & Woodward, 2003). Hamrick, Evans, & Schuh (2002) have focused on the fact that student affairs professionals incorporate the issues of diversity into their everyday tasks and work with an array of students in such areas as campus activities, counseling, resources, etc. This department, like others within the higher education system, seeks to serve the needs of the student (Bloland, 1979). Besides sufficient advice, anytime contact with the staffs' academic support also includes suggestion regarding study choice. A research study of Bronstein (2008) reveals that these academic support elements positively impacts on the students' perception regarding quality education.

3.0 Conceptual Model

From the above literature we have proposed a **research model** to define the factors affecting on the quality education. The resulting research model used in this paper is depicted below:

Figure 01: Conceptual model

4.0 Methodology of the Study

This part explains in detail about the methodology applied in this study. It highlights the type of research, sources of data used, and survey design which include sampling plan and data analysis method applied. This part is described in order to achieve a high degree of reliability and validity.

The identification of variables is done based on adopting exploratory research methods especially secondary data analysis and literature review. Now the study is carried out by the descriptive research design. In our study, we have used primary sources to analyze the data. The instrument used is a structured questionnaire that is developed based on the literature review on the relevant topics.

Target population consists of the students (elements) of public and private universities (extent) from whom the necessary data is collected to conduct multiple regressions analysis.

Every University maintains the detail students' information on their own database. It can be also called as students' register book. This students' register book is used as the sampling frame.

According to Malhotra, Ulgado, Agarwal, & Baalbaki (1994), the maximum number of stratum that can result in a significant analysis is 6. So, we have taken 4 universities for our study as stratum. Roscoe (1975) proposes that the appropriate sample sizes for most research to be greater than 30 and less than 500. Taking into considerations these guidelines, we have decided to choose 245 undergraduate students as our sample.

Stratified random sampling with proportional allocation is adopted to carry out the survey. Four Universities - Eastwest University, Daffodil International University, Faculty of Business Studies, University of Dhaka (DU) and Faculty of Business Studies, Jahangirnagar University (JU) are treated as a stratum. Strata are considered according to the nature of university (Public & Private). Eastwest University is graded as "A" category and Daffodil International University is graded as "B" category among the private universities. On the other hand University of Dhaka and Jahangirnagar University is very renowned among the public universities. Since BBA program are very popular among these four universities to the students of Business, we have selected to gather the required information from them. The details of the strata are presented here:

Table: 4.1 Distribution of sample according to stratum

Universities	Respondents
Faculty of Business Studies, DU	41%
Faculty of Business Studies, JU	14%
East west University	20%
Daffodil International University	25%
Total	100%

Sampling execution is done by conducting questionnaire in face-to-face approach at the end of the class. Any query to the respondents regarding the questionnaire is clarified on the spot. Respondents are allowed to ask for further clarification if they encountered difficulties to understand the questions. We have also managed to get 100% response from the respondents.

The survey instrument is consisted of two parts. Into the both parts, respondents are asked to state their level of agreement of each of the statement on a five-point likert scale (1 represent “strongly disagree” to 5 represent “strongly agree”; 3 denotes “neutral”).

We have used Multiple Regression for our data analysis. The Purpose of Multiple Regression Analysis is to measure the relative influence of each independent variable (Teaching Style, Assessment and Feedback, Academic Support, Organization and Management, Learning Resources, Personal Development) on the dependent variable (Perception on the education quality). Thus, following model is developed to test the significance of stated relationship. **The purpose of this analysis is to measure the relative influence of each independent variable on the dependent variable. The regression model that is used is as follows:**

$$Y (\text{Quality Education}) = b_0 + b_1 x_1 + b_2 x_2 + b_3 x_3 + b_4 x_4 + b_5 x_5 + b_6 x_6 + e_i$$

Where, Y= *Quality Education*

b_0 = Constant

x_1 = Teaching Quality

x_2 = Assessment and Feedback

x_3 = Academic Support

x_4 = Organization and Management

x_5 = Learning Resources

x_6 = Personal Development

e_i = Error term

The relative significance of each of the independent variable on the dependent variable can be measured from the associated coefficient.

5. 0 Findings and Analysis

We have applied stepwise multiple regression analysis to explain our findings. The purpose of this method is to select, from a large number of predictor variables, a small subset of variables that account for the most of the variation in the dependent or criterion variable.

5.1 Excluded Variables

Excluded Variables^f

Model	Beta In	t	Sig.	Partial Correlation	Collinearity Statistics
					Tolerance
1 Assessment and Feedback	.237 ^a	3.402	.001	.216	.537
Academic Support	.265 ^a	4.589	.000	.286	.750
Organizational and Management Approach	.244 ^a	4.536	.000	.283	.867
Learning Resources	.210 ^a	3.964	.000	.250	.913
Personal Development	.315 ^a	5.549	.000	.340	.750
2 Assessment and Feedback	.145 ^b	2.090	.038	.135	.496
Academic Support	.209 ^b	3.705	.000	.235	.718
Organizational and Management Approach	.198 ^b	3.798	.000	.240	.840
Learning Resources	.153 ^b	2.933	.004	.188	.865
3 Assessment and Feedback	.072 ^c	1.003	.317	.065	.448
Academic Support	.141 ^c	2.234	.026	.145	.567
Learning Resources	.125 ^c	2.435	.016	.157	.844
4 Assessment and Feedback	.063 ^d	.884	.377	.058	.446
Academic Support	.136 ^d	2.185	.030	.142	.566
5 Assessment and Feedback	.052 ^e	.737	.462	.048	.444

a. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), Teaching Quality

b. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), Teaching Quality, Personal Development

c. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), Teaching Quality, Personal Development, Organizational and Management Approach

d. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), Teaching Quality, Personal Development, Organizational and Management Approach, Learning Resources

e. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), Teaching Quality, Personal Development, Organizational and Management Approach, Learning Resources, Academic Support

f. Dependent Variable: Quality Education

From the above table we have found that independent variable **“Assessment and Feedback”** is excluded from the model because this variable is insignificant at 0.05 level. It implies that students do not consider Assessment and Feedback affects to the quality education. Collinearity Statistics shows that after excluding variables step by step

“Assessment and Feedback” has about 45% correlation with other variable. Therefore this variable is excluded from the model.

5.2 Strength of Association between Independent Variables and Dependent Variable, and Residual Analysis

Here the Predictors are: (Constant), Teaching Quality, Personal Development, Organizational and Management Approach, Learning Resources, Academic Support.

Model Summary^f

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.596 ^a	.356	.353	.874	
2	.656 ^b	.430	.425	.824	
3	.680 ^c	.463	.456	.801	
4	.690 ^d	.476	.467	.793	
5	.698 ^e	.487	.476	.787	2.051

a. Predictors: (Constant), Teaching Quality

b. Predictors: (Constant), Teaching Quality, Personal Development

c. Predictors: (Constant), Teaching Quality, Personal Development, Organizational and Management Approach

d. Predictors: (Constant), Teaching Quality, Personal Development, Organizational and Management Approach, Learning Resources

e. Predictors: (Constant), Teaching Quality, Personal Development, Organizational and Management Approach, Learning Resources, Academic Support

f. Dependent Variable: Quality Education

As the R² value is 0.487 which is not so closer to 1, it indicates there is moderate relationship between the dependent variable (**students’ perception on quality education**) and the independent variables (**Teaching Quality, Personal Development, Organizational and Management Approach, Learning Resources, Academic Support, Assessment and Feedback,**). It indicates that independent variables have the 48.7% ability to explain the dependent variable. Considering the model, the value of adjusted R² (0.476) is closer to the R² value and both are not so closer to 1. This suggests that adding each of the additional independent variables after the 1st independent variable, makes a significant contribution in explaining the variation in the dependent variable students’ Overall perception on the education quality.

Residuals Statistics^a

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	.93	4.86	3.39	.758	239
Residual	-2.258	2.118	.000	.778	239
Std. Predicted Value	-3.246	1.936	.000	1.000	239
Std. Residual	-2.871	2.693	.000	.989	239

a. Dependent Variable: Quality Education

Durbin-Watson statistics (2.051) indicates that the model is linear as the value lies within ± 4 . Residual Statistics shows that the Standard deviation of the error is about 99% where mean value is 0.000. So, we can say that error is normally distributed and assumptions are met and the linear model is appropriate.

5.3 Significance Test

ANOVA^f

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	99.851	1	99.851	130.774	.000 ^a
	Residual	180.960	237	.764		
	Total	280.812	238			
2	Regression	120.736	2	60.368	89.001	.000 ^b
	Residual	160.075	236	.678		
	Total	280.812	238			
3	Regression	129.994	3	43.331	67.518	.000 ^c
	Residual	150.818	235	.642		
	Total	280.812	238			
4	Regression	133.721	4	33.430	53.183	.000 ^d
	Residual	147.090	234	.629		
	Total	280.812	238			
5	Regression	136.674	5	27.335	44.187	.000 ^e
	Residual	144.138	233	.619		
	Total	280.812	238			

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Teaching Quality
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Teaching Quality, Personal Development
- c. Predictors: (Constant), Teaching Quality, Personal Development, Organizational and Management Approach
- d. Predictors: (Constant), Teaching Quality, Personal Development, Organizational and Management Approach, Learning Resources
- e. Predictors: (Constant), Teaching Quality, Personal Development, Organizational and Management Approach, Learning Resources, Academic Support
- f. Dependent Variable: Quality Education

From the above table it is found that the significance level of the F value (0.000001) is below $\alpha = 0.05$. At 5 & 233 degrees of freedom the calculated value of F is also greater than the table value. So it is proved that this regression model is significant. It indicates that the independent variables have significant relationship with the dependent variable. Thus the independent variables - (Constant), Teaching Quality, Personal Development, Organizational and Management Approach, Learning Resources, Academic Support have significant relationship with the dependent variable - Quality Education.

5.4 Coefficients Analysis

Analysis of co-efficient provides us which independent variables have significant relationship with the dependent variables and provide us the importance of each independent variable independently.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.023	.214		4.773	.000
	Teaching Quality	.664	.058	.596	11.436	.000
2	(Constant)	.379	.233		1.624	.106
	Teaching Quality	.488	.063	.439	7.730	.000
	Personal Development	.332	.060	.315	5.549	.000
3	(Constant)	.142	.235		.603	.547
	Teaching Quality	.429	.063	.386	6.769	.000
	Personal Development	.292	.059	.277	4.936	.000

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	Organizational and Management Approach	.196	.052	.198	3.798	.000
4	(Constant)	-.044	.245		-.179	.858
	Teaching Quality	.411	.063	.370	6.515	.000
	Personal Development	.263	.060	.249	4.392	.000
	Organizational and Management Approach	.177	.052	.179	3.416	.001
	Learning Resources	.123	.051	.125	2.435	.016
5	(Constant)	-.052	.243		-.216	.829
	Teaching Quality	.369	.066	.331	5.623	.000
	Personal Development	.245	.060	.233	4.102	.000
	Organizational and Management Approach	.120	.057	.121	2.087	.038
	Learning Resources	.120	.050	.122	2.389	.018
	Academic Support	.127	.058	.136	2.185	.030

a. Dependent Variable: Quality Education

Here, we see that Teaching Quality (0.000), Personal Development (0.000), Organizational and Management Approach (0.038), Learning Resources (0.018), Academic Support (0.030) significantly [Significant at 0.05 level] affect to the Quality Education. The relative coefficient of independent variables describes the relative importance to contribute the Quality Education. Therefore, the following regression model is formulated:

$$\text{Students' perception on Quality Education } (\hat{Y}) = -0.052 + 0.369*\text{Teaching Quality} + 0.127*\text{Academic Support} + 0.120*\text{Organizational and Management Support} + 0.120*\text{Learning Resources} + 0.245*\text{Personal Development}$$

Thus, we can conclude that

- ◆ *Education quality depends on Teaching Quality, Personal Development, Organizational and Management Approach, Learning Resources, Academic Support.*
- ◆ *Teaching Quality is the most significant factor to ensure the quality education followed by Personal Development, Organizational and Management Approach, Learning Resources, Academic Support.*
- ◆ *Assessment and Feedback mechanism in the institution is the only factor which is not considered as the criteria to ensure the quality education*

6.0 Conclusion

Education is the backbone of any nation. Government of every country tries to provide better education to the general public. The consequence of this notion is resulted the approval of private university to ensure higher education. It is not possible for any government to ensure 100% higher education to all the public. Here the private university is playing major role to provide these services.

But ensuring quality education of private university sometimes is in question mark. Some private universities are charging higher tuition fee rather than providing quality education. Taking into account of this fact, authorities of private universities should be aware of quality education and thereafter try to ensure quality with higher tuition fee.

Our research has revealed five important factors among the six identified factors to ensure the quality education. Qualified faculties play the most important role here. Teaching methods, in-depth knowledge about the course, communication skills etc. are the significant criteria to become a qualified teacher. In addition to this factor, Self-Development includes - analytical ability, presentation skill, English proficiency skills, subjective knowledge are the sign of personal achievement of the students. Students need to interact with the administrative employees for the support activities. It is observed that administrative officers do not cooperate with the students properly and also they sometimes involve in malpractices. So, Organizational and Management Approach should be very friendly and prompt and responsive. Another significant factor to ensure quality education is availability of Learning Resources. It defines mostly the library facilities and IT Facilities of the university. Finally, Academic Support is necessary to improve the students quality and helpful for choosing the right career track. Career Counseling, Job placement, Career Training Programs etc. are beneficial to foster the performance and skills of the students.

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